

CYBERLENINKA

BASE

OpenAIRE

Google Scholar

SHARQ FALSAFASI CERTIFICATE

OF PARTICIPATION

THIS CERTIFICATE IS PROUDLY PRESENTED TO

Siddiqov N.N

YATROGENIK KASALLIKLAR. ULARNING PAYDO BÖLISHI. TIBBIY SIR.

DRJI

 Universal
Impact Factor

WEBSITE: WWW.REANDPUB.UZ

INDEX COPERNICUS
INTERNATIONAL

2023-2024

 zenodo

EMAIL: INFO@REANDPUB.UZ

 ADVANCED SCIENCE INDEX